

Looking at Folk Biology from the Perspective of Cognitive Folklore

Bilişsel Folklor Penceresinden Halk Biyolojisine Bakmak

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Abstract

This study focuses on the relationship between folk biology and folklore through the emerging framework of cognitive folklore. While folk biology examines how humans intuitively classify and reason about living species, cognitive folklore reveals how these cognitive processes are expressed, transmitted, and transformed through traditional narratives, beliefs, and rituals. Drawing on examples from folklore such as animal symbolism, sacred plants, and metamorphosis myths, this article argues that folklore serves a cognitive function, both reflecting and organizing human understanding of the natural world. Integrating insights from cognitive anthropology, psychology, and folklore studies, this study demonstrates that traditional representations of nature are cognitively grounded models of biological knowledge. Consequently, cognitive folklore offers a powerful interdisciplinary perspective for understanding how humans think, feel, and remember the living world.

Keywords: cognitive folklore, folk biology, ecology, culture, intuition.

Öz

Bu çalışma, bilişsel folklorun ortaya çıkan çerçevesi aracılığıyla halk biyolojisi ve folklor arasındaki ilişkiye odaklanmıştır. Halk biyolojisi, insanların canlı türlerini sezgisel olarak nasıl sınıflandırdığını ve akıl yürüttüğünü incelerken, bilişsel folklor bu bilişsel süreçlerin geleneksel anlatılar, inançlar ve ritüeller aracılığıyla nasıl ifade edildiğini, aktarıldığını ve dönüştürüldüğünü ortaya koymaktadır. Hayvan sembolizmi, kutsal bitkiler ve metamorfoz efsaneleri gibi folklorlardan örneklere yer veren bu makale, folklorun hem insanın doğal dünyayı anlamasını yansıtan hem de düzenleyen bilişsel bir işlev gördüğünü savunmaktadır. Bilişsel antropoloji, psikoloji ve folklor çalışmalarından elde edilen içgörülerini bütünleştiren bu çalışma, doğanın geleneksel temsillerinin biyolojik bilginin bilişsel olarak temellendirilmiş

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modelleri olduđunu göstermektedir. Sonuç olarak, bilişsel folklor, insanların canlılar dünyasını nasıl düşündüğünü, hissettiğini ve hatırladığını anlamak için güçlü bir disiplinlerarası bakış açısı sunmaktadır.

Anahtar Sözcükler: bilişsel folklor, halk biyolojisi, ekoloji, kültür, sezgi.

Introduction

The natural world has always held a central place in the human imagination. Within their cultural contexts, people have developed complex systems of knowledge about plants, animals, and ecological processes, and modern science has only recently begun to study these systems. In this context, in recent years, the dialogue between cognitive sciences and folklore studies has revealed new perspectives on how traditional knowledge is structured, transmitted, and remembered. Among these, the relationship between folk biology – a concept emerging from cognitive anthropology – and the cognitive dimensions of folklore offers a particularly fertile ground for interdisciplinary research. Folk biology concerns how people from different cultures perceive, classify, and reason about living beings in their natural environments (Atran, 1998: 548-49). This discipline examines the ways in which people form intuitive classifications about plants and animals and the mental templates that underpin these classifications. Cognitive folklore aims to uncover the mental mechanisms and cultural logics that shape the formation and continuity of folkloric forms such as myths, proverbs, riddles, folktales, and folk poetry. Examining folk biology from a cognitive folklore perspective allows us to explore how culturally transmitted knowledge about the world of living beings is organized in the human mind and expressed through symbolic forms.

The origins of folk biology as an analytical framework trace back to the work of Scott Atran (1990) and Brent Berlin (1992), who demonstrated that local biological classification systems are neither arbitrary nor purely linguistic structures but are instead based on universal cognitive principles. According to their findings, people tend to divide living beings into hierarchically structured groups (genera, species, life forms, etc.) based on perceptual and functional salience. However, this cognitive taxonomy is shaped by cultural contexts. Cultural elements imbue biological categories with moral and spiritual meanings. Thus, while the human mind possesses

innate tendencies to classify nature, folklore provides a symbolic medium that lends narrative and sensory depth to these classifications.

Cognitive approaches to folklore, influenced by researchers such as Dan Ben-Amos (1971), Alan Dundes (1965), Pascal Boyer (1994), and Jesper Sørensen (2007), have emphasized that folkloric traditions are not merely cultural residues but are adapted expressions of cognitive patterns. Folklore encodes mnemonic structures—such as stories, analogies, and metaphors—that help communities preserve and transmit knowledge about their environment. Proverbs about animal behavior, myths explaining the origins of plants, or rituals and taboos related to specific species can be interpreted as cognitive tools for organizing and stabilizing ecological knowledge. Looking at folk biology through the lens of cognitive folklore allows for an understanding of how biological knowledge is embodied within a community’s collective imagination. Cognitive mechanisms such as categorization, memory, and schema theory help explain oral tradition. As Pascal Boyer (1994: 62-64) noted, traditional narratives serve as a cognitive map and mnemonic function at the intersection of biological knowledge and symbolic imagination.

Theoretical Framework

Understanding folklore as a cognitive phenomenon based on universal mental mechanisms, representational formats, and memory processes, rather than merely a social and aesthetic one, is likely a more accurate approach from the perspective of contemporary understandings of folklore. The concept we refer to as “cognitive folklore” assumes that traditional narratives, rituals, and belief systems are shaped by the mental principles governing everyday reasoning and memory. Therefore, it provides a useful framework for investigating how the human mind organizes and transmits cultural knowledge, including knowledge of the natural world that lies at the heart of folk biology (Siikala, 1990; Dégh, 1995; D’Andrade, 1995).

Folk biology emerged from cognitive anthropology in the 1970s and 1980s, primarily through the work of Brent Berlin and Scott Atran. Their studies revealed that indigenous societies classify plants and animals according to a set of cognitive regularities that are strikingly consistent across cultures. Berlin’s ethnobiological classification (1992) demonstrated that people use a limited number of hierarchical taxonomic levels (life form, ge-

nus, and species) based on perceptual salience and utility. Atran (1990) expanded this model by proposing that these systems stem from intuitive biology—a universal cognitive domain specialized for reasoning about living beings.

Cognitive approaches to folklore developed as a response to the limitations of purely structural or contextual models. Dan Ben-Amos's (1971) emphasis on the "contextual" aspects of folklore was later developed by researchers who highlighted the cognitive foundations of context itself—that is, how people perceive, process, and remember cultural forms. For example, Alan Dundes's (1965) concept of the "motif" can be seen as a mental template organizing narrative content. More recently, researchers like Pascal Boyer (1994) and Jesper Sørensen (2007) have applied cognitive and evolutionary theories to explain why certain types of stories, symbols, and rituals persist across cultures. These scholars argue that folklore endures because it fits the structure of the human mind. Cognitive constraints shape what is memorable, attention-grabbing, and culturally transmissible. Within his concept of minimal counter-intuitiveness, Boyer proposed that anomalous representations (e.g., talking animals, divine beings, etc.) are generated due to their function of being more easily remembered (1994).

Cognitive processes such as perception, classification, schema formation, and memory operate at the intersection of mental structures and cultural features. For instance, folk tales about animals often reflect folk biological taxonomies: predators are portrayed as cunning, while herbivores are depicted as naive or innocent, demonstrating intuitive reasoning about species' behaviors. Proverbs and folk beliefs encode ecological regularities, such as the connection between seasonal changes and animal habits, and preserve experiential observations in memorable form. While the human ability to classify other living beings appears to be a universal feature of human cognition, its manifestations are, in fact, culturally specific.

Folk Biology and Folklore

Proverbs are among the richest sources of folk biological knowledge. They distill ecological observations spanning generations into concise, memorable phrases that are cognitively easy to learn and transmit. In agrarian societies where daily life depends on close attention to animal and plant behaviors, proverbs often serve as reminders of seasonal and environmental cycles. Traditional weather lore is also related to this. Cognitive folklore

interprets these proverbs and folk knowledge as evidence of the human mind's tendency to attribute social meanings to biological regularities.

Myths and legends transport themes such as human-animal relationships, plant growth, and the changing of seasons into the realm of imagination through anthropomorphism and personification. Motifs like talking animals, supernatural beings, and shape-shifting humans are cognitively compelling because they combine minimal counter-intuitive behavior with biological expectations. As Pascal Boyer argued, such minimally counter-intuitive entities are more likely to be remembered and transmitted because they slightly violate the mind's intuitive ontologies while still largely interacting with them. Similarly, myths of sacred trees are based on the cognitive salience of trees as vertically structured life forms connecting the earth and the sky. These symbolic elaborations reveal how human cognition extends folk biological categories into cosmological domains. Thus, folklore becomes a cognitive phenomenon where biological perception, symbolic imagination, and cultural identity converge.

Ritual practices also illustrate the interaction between cognitive universals and cultural specifics within folk biology. Taboos related to killing or consuming certain species — such as sacred plants, totemic animals, or birds associated with ancestors — reflect the mental distinction between ordinary and special categories of beings. From a cognitive perspective, these taboos reveal a dual ontological status attributed to an organism, encompassing both the natural and the social. In Turkish Shamanism, for example, the bear and the eagle have often been viewed as spiritual intermediaries between the human and non-human realms. Their status corresponds to their perceptual and behavioral distinctiveness, all of which has rendered them cognitively marked.

The continuity of folk biological motifs across generations can be explained by cognitive mechanisms like memory and schema formation. People more easily recall narratives and proverbs that fit into pre-existing mental schemas than those that do not. Since all humans share an intuitive biological understanding, such as recognizing species, behaviors, and ecological roles, folkloric materials based on these domains are transmitted from generation to generation. Ancestral myths explaining why the crow is black or why the fox is cunning endure because they are cognitively anchored in observable biological realities.

Viewed from this perspective, folklore and folk biology exist in a dynamic interplay between perception, classification, memory, and imagination. Folklore transforms human experience with living species into a symbolic order; it enables biological facts to become metaphors, ecological observations to become narratives, and daily interactions with nature to become expressions of identity and worldview. Thus, the question becomes not only how people think about nature, but how they think through it.

The binary oppositions inherent in the human mind (good-evil, cunning-naive, black-white, etc.) are manifested through linguistic structures (Rosch, 1978) and they persist within folkloric products as well. When a wolf appears in a narrative, listeners immediately activate cognitive schemas associated with danger, wilderness, and predatory animals. There are, for example, no prototypical schemas like “cute, friendly, companion” for this animal. This allows the narrative to be built upon deeply ingrained mental models without requiring explicit explanation. This kind of prototypical thinking also explains why certain animals are dominant in oral traditions. Similarly, the tree, as a symbol of life or the world axis, holds a cognitive position as a metaphor for cosmic order and the continuity of lineage.

In the Turkish belief system, trees such as the pomegranate, willow, plane, poplar, cypress, and beech are also grasped through a cognitive prototype. Social meanings related to human life—such as death, eternity, fertility, and rebirth—become prominent in relation to them. Knowledge about entities that evoke strong emotional or perceptual responses through such symbolic associations is remembered and transmitted. Folklore subsequently reinforces these associations through ritual and narrative repetition.

In addition, it is necessary to mention another recurring motif in world folklore: metamorphosis narratives dealing with the transformation between human and non-human forms. Motifs involving transformation from human to animal, stone, tree, or plant, by slightly violating intuitive expectations about biological boundaries, make them more memorable and striking. Cognitive theory explains their appeal through the concept of minimal counter-intuitiveness.

Conclusion

Folk taxonomies—the local classifications of living species—demonstrate the interaction between cognition and culture. Ethnobiological studies in Anatolia show that local communities often organize species into hierarchies similar to scientific taxonomy, but according to perceptual and utilitarian criteria (For instance, domesticated and utilized animals are classified as “*mal*” [property], while others are called “*hayvan*” [animal]). Terms like herb, tree, or bird function as generic-level categories roughly equivalent to scientific genera. Within these categories, more detailed distinctions can be made based on habitat, color, or use.

Folklore is a representational system that both reflects and regulates humanity’s interaction with the natural world; it stabilizes intuitive biological concepts, transforms them into symbolic narratives, and transmits them in socially meaningful ways. Cognitive folklore uncovers the mental map underlying these processes, allowing us to see how people think about and through nature. Folk biology provides the empirical foundation for this cognitive system. Here, traditional knowledge about living beings is revealed as a manifestation of cognitive structures that show how the natural world is perceived, categorized, and remembered. It is at this juncture that cognitive folklore emerges as a candidate for being a form of ecological reasoning—one that merges the boundaries between mind, culture, and nature within a symbolic order.

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Additional Information

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